

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MILITARY-PATRIOTIC QUALITIES IN STUDENTS BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH

Kh.Yu.Mirzakarimov

Head of pre-conscription training for young men of School
№ 11 in Tashlak district of Fergana region.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17897287>

Abstract: this article presents information on innovative teaching methods aimed at developing military-patriotic qualities in students, as well as the pedagogical possibilities of their application in the training process.

Key words: Innovative teaching methods, modular education, student-centered educational technologies.

Within the framework of the tasks defined in the conceptual-methodological and organizational-pedagogical block of the requirements of the Concept for Ensuring the Continuity of Educational Programs in Secondary Schools, Vocational Schools, Academic Lyceums, and Higher Education Systems for the subject "Pre-conscription Initial Training" and the model of research work, based on the axiological priority of the principle of a historical approach to the heritage of ancestors in the process of developing the military-patriotic qualities of students, the effectiveness of the use of the following innovative educational technologies and methods in the process of conducting classes in the module "History of Military Patriotism and Military Art" (lectures, practical, seminar, and independent study), included in the program of the subject "Organization of Pre-conscription Initial Training and Methods of its Teaching," was revealed.

Modular learning technology represents the application of technology to the components of the educational process related to military-patriotic education. This technology was aimed at solving specific didactic and educational tasks.

In educational technologies for military-patriotic education, the student is placed at the center of the pedagogical educational process, favorable conditions are created for his development and the realization of his natural potential.

One of the most effective and promising technologies of personality-oriented learning technology is modular learning technology. The application of modular educational technology in teaching specialized disciplines in the process of developing military-patriotic qualities in students is based on the idea of ensuring their independent and systematic work on self-improvement. Modular learning technology improves the student's creative activity in the military-patriotic process.

A module is a logically complete set of educational material, built on developed principles and aimed at studying one or more basic concepts of a subject. In the research process, students rely on the complementary features of the modules of the discipline "Organization of Pre-Conscription Initial Training and Methods of its Teaching" (lecture, practical, seminar, and independent study).

In the modular teaching method, the theoretical and practical aspects of the subject, which have common aspects, are interconnected and complement each other, are divided into separate parts.

It was taken into account that each module must provide holistic and complete knowledge and, of course, have a block of criteria for determining the results.

The module program consisted of a complex didactic goal and a set of modular blocks serving to achieve this goal. To develop a modular program, it is necessary to identify the main ideas and structure them in block modules, and then formulate a complex of didactic goals.

In improving the module, we focused on three main components:

1) specificity of the module; 2) the presence of a control unit of the module; 3) development of didactic materials of the module.

The content of the module "History of Military Patriotism and Military Art" consists of:

1. Formation of the history of military art. Military and national values in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan: commanders who contributed to the development of the military sphere on a global scale. The Role of Great Commanders in the History of Military Art. The Essence of the Concepts of Patriotism and Military Patriotism. Deeply instilling in the minds of young people the military heritage of our national heroes and forming in their consciousness a sense of respect for the glorious history of our nation, pride in our Armed Forces. The role of general education schools in educating students in the spirit of military patriotism.

2. The role and contributions of our great commanders Amir Temur, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, and Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur in the history of the development of military art: The unique military talent of Sahibkiran Amir Temur. The composition, structure, and procedure for recruiting Amir Timur's army. The importance of "Timur's Code" in the military sphere. Jalaluddin Manguberdi's feats for the defense of the homeland. Deeply instilling in the minds of young people the military heritage of the invincible commander Jaloliddin Manguberdi and forming in them a sense of national pride and honor. Zahiriddin Muhammad

Babur was a connoisseur of military science. Babur's enormous contribution to the development of intelligence and artillery.

In addition, this module provides for practical, seminar, and independent study sessions. In the course of the research work, the following materials were prepared for the module: teaching aids necessary for lectures, practical and seminar classes, handouts, tests for monitoring students' knowledge, questionnaires, electronic materials for independent work.

In order to ensure the effectiveness of the module, interactive educational technologies were also intensively used in the training process.

Interactive educational technologies serve to activate the assimilation of knowledge and the development of personal qualities by increasing the activity of the student and the teacher in the educational process.

Through the application of interactive methods in the educational process, the ability of students to create new and original ideas, creative problem-solving, the ability to apply unusual and effective methods in problem-solving (creativity), analysis, drawing conclusions (reflection), healthy communication (communicativeness), knowledge of basic information and facts, the ability to understand and interpret information, the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in practice, the ability to analyze information and determine their interrelationships, the ability to combine various information and create new ideas (cognitive thinking), to draw attention to the main issues of the educational problem, to develop the skills of discussion and discussion, and the necessary conditions are created for the ability of students to demonstrate their capabilities.

Interactivity, in essence, means the ability of students to organize joint actions based on mutual cooperation in the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, abilities, and certain moral qualities. From a logical point of view, interaction, first of all, represents a conversation (dialogue) of social subjects, actions, activities based on mutual cooperation.

By improving the possibilities of integrating interactive teaching methods in the development of military-patriotic qualities in students, we mean the effectiveness of traditional forms and methods of education used today in the process of military-patriotic education and upbringing of students, the possibilities of effective use of interactive teaching methods and technologies (such as "Active Seminar," "Filler" technology, "Stimulating Ideas," "Quick Survey," "Concept Analysis," "Mutual Learning in a Team") used in lectures, seminars, practical classes, without denying their possibilities.

After the completion of the assimilation process, it was determined under what conditions the student could perform the activity. The results have an organic unity and are formed without deviating from the learning objectives. In the process of checking the results, the acquisition of several skills was envisioned. During the study, the following four criteria were identified that measure the level of development: creative, activity-based, cognitive, and motivational. Based on these criteria, the following indicators were developed that determine the development of military-patriotic qualities in students.

Table 1.

Indicators determining the development of military-patriotic qualities in students.

Cognitive	- knowledge of basic information and facts, the ability to understand and interpret data, the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in practice, the ability to analyze data and identify their interrelationships, combine various data and generate new ideas.
	- motives: students' internal interest in learning based on their specific interests and needs.
	- the ability to understand and apply theoretical knowledge in practice.
Motivational	- the ability to create new and original ideas, creatively solve problems: the ability to apply unusual and effective methods in solving problems; - creative collaboration: the development of the ability to work collectively and cooperate with others in creative processes.

References used:

1. Р.Мавлонова ва бошқалар. Педагогика назарияси ва тарихи. Т.: “Фан ва технологиялар” 2010 йил.
2. А.Миноваров. Педагогика. Т.: “Ўқитувчи” 1996 йил.
3. Ш.Тилаволдиев, А.Акбаров. Ҳарбий ватанпарварлик тарбияси асослари. Фарғона. 2003 йил

